

Review

Understanding Urban Cooling of Blue–Green Infrastructure: A Review of Spatial Data and Sustainable Planning Optimization Methods for Mitigating Urban Heat Islands

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Abstract: Many studies in the literature have assessed the blue–green infrastructure (BGI) characteristics that influence its cooling potential for sustainable urban development. Common assessment methods include satellite remote sensing, numerical simulations, and field measurements, each defining different cooling efficiency indicators. This methodological diversity creates uncertainties in optimizing BGI management. To address this, a literature review was conducted using Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus, examining how the BGI cools urban space, which spatial data and methods are most effective, which methodological differences may affect the results, and what the current research gaps and innovative future directions are. The results suggest that remote sensing is ideal for large-scale BGI comparisons, numerical simulations for local development scenarios, and field measurements for assessing conditions closest to residents. Maximum BGI cooling intensity averages show 4 °C from remote sensing, 3 °C from field measurements, and 2 °C from numerical simulations. Differences in conclusions may arise from differences in the data resolution, model scale, BGI delineation method, and cooling range calculation. The key BGI characteristics include object size, vegetation fraction, foliage density, and spatial connectivity. Future research should prioritize the integration of the different methods, BGI shape complexity effectiveness assessment, and effects of urban morphology on evaluating BGI characteristics' effectiveness, and explore digital twin technology for BGI management optimization. This study integrates key information on BGI's cooling capabilities, serving as a useful resource for both practitioners and researchers to support resilient city development.

Keywords: sustainable urban development; blue–green infrastructure; climate adaptation; urban cool island; urban heat island; remote sensing; simulation; computational fluid dynamics; field measurements; digital twin

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1. Introduction and Background

Climate change is causing increasingly frequent, intense, and prolonged heat waves (HWs) [1–3], which severely impact human society, quality of life, mortality [4–7], the economy [8], ecosystems [9,10], and energy consumption [11]. During the summer heatwave of 2003 in Western Europe alone, over 70,000 additional deaths were recorded [12]. In cities, which feature unique land use morphology and specific relationships between incoming and outgoing energy flows in the surface system, this trend is intensified by the formation

of urban heat islands (UHIs) [13–16]. Urban conditions, along with population aging, high population density, and concentrated infrastructure, leave cities especially vulnerable to the negative effects of HWs. Addressing these challenges requires the pursuit of cost-effective urban solutions that influence urbanization patterns to mitigate negative impacts, adapt to climate change, and improve quality of life.

To mitigate HW-related risks by regulating urbanization processes, critical means can be offered by spatial planning [17–23]. Within this sector, and in conjunction with landscape architecture, economics, and ecological engineering, the concept of ecosystem services has emerged, representing the multidimensional benefits people gain from urban natural capital, based on the blue–green infrastructure (BGI) [24–32]. In this context, the BGI was developed as a tool to counteract the negative effects of climate change, including HWs and UHIs. The BGI comprises (1) natural and artificial hydrographic elements, such as rivers, reservoirs, wetlands, and marshes; (2) all vegetated areas, including public parks and gardens, forests, squares, etc.; and (3) vegetation-based hydrological engineering solutions, including rain gardens, green roofs, and retention–infiltration basins [33,34] that facilitate rainwater infiltration, filtration, and purification through processes such as plant root absorption, soil infiltration, and microbial decomposition within substrates and vegetation mounted on specific structures. BGI cooling mainly comes from vegetation’s evapotranspiration, shading, and wind flow modification, which enable evapotranspiration and convective cooling [35], leading to local microclimate improvements and reductions in building energy consumption. Additionally, BGI cooling capacity can be further enhanced by reducing rainwater runoff through soil retention and interception by vegetation, controlled by the action of leaf surface adhesion, gravity, and the cohesion of water molecules [36]. For example, extensive green roofs can intercept, retain, and consequently evaporate 34–69% of precipitation [37], providing more effective cooling.

The literature includes numerous studies evaluating the effectiveness of BGI in mitigating UHIs, using related terms such as park cool island, water cool island, and urban cool island (UCI), which refer to phenomena where specific BGI components have lower temperatures than impervious surfaces [38–43]. These studies have assessed BGI characteristics for their cooling potential, supporting sustainable spatial policies [44–46]. Unfortunately, the variety of research methods may limit optimal implementation, creating uncertainty and confining conclusions to local findings only [47]. The main categories of methods for assessing BGI effectiveness include (1) on-site air temperature (T-air) measurements to evaluate “air” UHI mitigation; (2) remote sensing of land surface temperature (LST) related to surface UHIs (SUHIs), often using satellite data; and (3) numerical modeling of T-air at micro, local, and mesoscale levels [15,47–49], with primary thermal data sources on urban areas, like LST and T-air, being not correlated [50–56]. Additionally, numerous indicators have emerged over time, defining BGI’s cooling potential in various ways. The remote sensing approach generally compares LST inside and around BGI to measure the cooling distance and intensity at the outermost urban surface layer. Numerical simulations usually analyze mean T-air changes before and after BGI implementation, with models at different scales applying distinct assumptions regarding heat exchange processes, and different temporal contexts (e.g., diurnal average vs. noontime cooling) leading to diverse outcomes. Field measurements, on the other hand, often focus on T-air differences at specific locations within and near BGI at a human level [47].

This methodological diversity increases uncertainty in forming conclusions about effective BGI design, as it can become a key factor—alongside geographical, climatic, and weather conditions—in creating variation in results. Consequently, for example, research based on T-air generally indicates that vegetation provides a better cooling effect than water [57–60], while LST-based studies show the opposite [60–62]. Moreover, some

studies indicate that the complexity of BGI shapes may positively influence the cooling potential [63–67], while others suggest a negative impact [44,46,62,68,69]. Furthermore, notable variation exists within each method type: (1) satellite remote sensing results show BGI cooling ranges between 18 and 4000 m, depending on data sources and LST downscaling level [63,70–72]; (2) numerical simulations report a cooling effectiveness from <1 to 18.4 °C, even after standardization based on vegetation fraction [47]; and (3) T-air field measurements indicate maximum cooling ranges of 180–860 m, with intensity levels in the range of 0.14–8.8 °C [39,73–78].

For optimal planning and management of BGI, it is essential to organize and systematize existing research findings, including the potential impact of different research methods and data types. The wide variety of research techniques also points to the need for unified methodological frameworks to optimize BGI planning and management. Given advances in computational capabilities, these frameworks should leverage promising technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), Big Data (BD), and the Internet of Things (IoT), which have the potential to enhance decision-support tools for BGI towards a more holistic approach. This framing can aid decision makers and practitioners in interpreting results and help researchers to identify existing gaps and the most promising future research directions, ultimately leading to more effective BGI development strategies and stronger urban resilience against HWs.

Considering the aforementioned issues and uncertainties, the primary aim of this article is to systematize the knowledge on using geoinformatics tools and spatial data in studying the cooling potential of BGI for spatial planning through the following actions:

1. Present the mechanisms behind the formation of BGI's cooling abilities;
2. Discuss the most effective BGI features that positively impact cooling potential, regardless of method;
3. Examine the characteristics of spatial data and geoinformatics methods used in analyzing BGI's cooling effects, with attention to potential impacts on result variability;
4. Propose promising future research directions for optimizing BGI planning and management processes.

2. Materials and Methods

The methodology is based on a literature review, focusing on four areas: remote sensing, numerical simulations, field measurements, and emerging technologies. Literature searches were conducted using Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus, up to November 2024, with keywords related to the quantitative assessment of urban BGI cooling using common methods. Various combinations of the following phrases were used to search titles, keywords, and abstracts: “green”, “blue”, “infrastructure”, “water”, “vegetation”, “city”, “urban”, “heat island”, “cooling”, “cooling island”, “cooling potential”, “cooling effect”, “air temperature”, “land surface temperature”, “factors”, “method”, “technology”, “modeling”, “smart cities”, “remote sensing”, “simulation”, “field measurements”, “transect”, “traverse”, “morphology”, “local climate zones”, and “digital twin”.

The review included 306 references, selected for their relevance to mechanisms and key features affecting BGI cooling effectiveness, characteristics of methods for quantifying BGI effectiveness that may influence the magnitude of cooling, and future research directions related to BGI management. Once the literature was selected, information was gathered at a progressive level (titles, then abstracts, then keywords, and finally full texts) according to the following criteria: (1) the study is urban-focused, meaning that the study area is localized in an urbanized area or covers the entire city, and the study object is related to urban ecosystem services (such as UHI mitigation), and (2) for objectives 2 and 3, the study quantitatively assesses BGI characteristics, which involves the use of specific quantitative

indicators for analysis (area or shape type measured by means of geoinformatics techniques, vegetation cover calculated using a specific vegetation index, greenery height determined by means of laser scanning, etc.). The consistency and accuracy of these standards in the review process was ensured by matching the extracted results to homogeneous tables containing all the required information. In addition, efforts were made to balance the research between different geographical regions. Once the literature was collected and checked for consistency with the assumptions made, the articles were included in the review and comparisons.

This review addresses BGI planning and management comprehensively—from current urban thermal assessment methods and mechanisms shaping BGI cooling to BGI characteristics that enhance cooling potential, considering both BGI-specific features and urban morphology. It also details geoinformatics methods for evaluating BGI cooling, covering BGI representation models, cooling potential metrics, spatial data sources, and potential tool development directions with a focus on promising technologies.

3. Existing Methods for Assessing the Thermal Characteristics of Urban Areas

To better understand how BGI cools urban spaces, it is essential to outline basic concepts describing urban thermal characteristics, particularly the UHI phenomenon. The UHI effect can arise from climatic processes within both the urban boundary layer (UBL) and the urban canopy layer (UCL) [79,80]. This effect is most intense under anticyclonic conditions, especially during heatwaves, when increased solar radiation raises the energy stored in the urban environment, and at night, when heat release from urban surfaces becomes the primary contributor [35,79]. UHI studies focus on two main areas: (1) “air” UHIs, describing thermal differences within the atmospheric boundary and canopy layers, and (2) “surface” UHIs (SUHIs), analyzing temperature contrasts between urbanized and non-urbanized surfaces [15,48,49]. Importantly, in cities, surface temperatures can be completely different from T-air [50–56].

The measurement of atmospheric UHIs, which can most effectively reflect potential risks, involves the use of sensors on fixed meteorological stations or mobile traverse methods to assess T-air differences within the UCL, or more advanced platforms such as tall towers, radiosondes, or aircraft-mounted temperature sensors to study UBL heat island [49,81–83]. Importantly, T-air plays a crucial role in urban energy balance and affects direct heat perception [50,84]. However, relying solely on ground station T-air measurements can be inadequate for capturing fine-scale temperature variations within cities due to their sparse spatial distribution, often leading to an underestimation of the temperature effects [85]. However, with self-programmed measurements, it is possible to track the actual intensity of the UHI in dense time series and vertical profiles.

Conversely, SUHI research heavily relies on satellite-based thermal remote sensing data, affording consistent and replicable evaluations of LST dynamics [50,86,87]. However, LST only reflects the energy exchange between the land surface, atmospheric insulation, and solar radiation [88–90]. This process influences near-surface T-air, evapotranspiration, and atmospheric humidity [91], slightly affecting the perceived temperature [92]. Relying solely on LST may not be sufficient for capturing the complex thermal dynamics of urban environments. Thermal sensors indirectly gauge the temperature of the outermost layer of urban surfaces (tree canopies, rooftops, etc.) by detecting upward long-wave radiation, with shaded areas under, for example, buildings and trees being undetectable [93,94], and various thermodynamic and radiative properties significantly impacting the detection process [48,50,54]. Additionally, atmospheric absorption can consume radiation [53], and some atmospheric radiation may reach sensors without directly interacting with the surface [48].

Alongside real-world measurements, the literature also identifies an additional UHI research approach—numerical simulations of T-air and other urban atmospheric characteristics [47]. Commonly used approaches within this methodology include local computational fluid dynamics (CFD) [95,96] models and energy balance models (EBMs) [47,97,98], as well as mesoscale atmospheric models, such as WRF [47,99–101]. The most well-known CFD models include OpenFOAM, FLUENT, STAR-CCM+, PHOENICS, and ENVI-met. In the case of EBMs, notable models include RayMan, SOLWEIG, green-CTTC, and TEB-Veg [98]. However, these methods do not reflect actual measurements and may therefore be subject to greater uncertainty.

Despite the variety of methods available for assessing UHI and UCI, the most effective and therefore the most commonly used are field measurements, satellite remote sensing, and CFD numerical simulations (primarily using ENVI-met for UCI).

4. Factors Determining the Cooling Potential of BGI

4.1. Micro-Scale Properties of BGI Affecting Cooling Potential

Through mechanisms like transpiration, shading, absorbing direct and diffuse shortwave radiation and longwave radiation from surrounding surfaces and the atmosphere, heat conduction to subsurface, and the modification of airflow, vegetation plays a pivotal role in urban energy balance, alleviating the UHI effect [35,102–105]. Evapotranspiration through BGI development can replace sensible heating with latent heating, leading to evaporative cooling (releasing latent heat), effectively lowering ambient temperatures by up to 4 °C [102]. The urban space cooling process, performed by vegetation, is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of urban space cooling performed by vegetation. Based on Oke [106].

The cooling potential of transpiration can vary based on plant species and is influenced by photosynthetic metabolism [35]. Most plants utilize C3 photosynthetic metabolism, which requires leaf stomata to remain open only during the day for transpiration, while plants in much warmer climates often exhibit crassulacean acid metabolism, a type of C4 photosynthesis that conserves water by opening stomata only at night [74]. Additionally, factors such as crown area, leaf characteristics, leaf height above the ground, stomatal resistance, and the hydraulic resistances of shoots and roots significantly influence transpiration

rates. These factors vary by species and are further affected by soil conditions, including water content and availability, compaction, and hydraulic conductivity [107]. For instance, in a Central European climate, *Tilia cordata* trees can provide four times more transpiration compared to *Robinia pseudoacacia*, reducing the T-air by up to 2.8 °C compared to 1.9 °C, with a leaf area index (LAI) 35% higher in *Tilia cordata* [108]. In tropical climates, *Bauhinia purpurea* trees, with an LAI of 2.76, can lower the T-air by 3.28 °C, whereas *Elaeocarpus hygrophilus*, with an LAI of 0.59, achieves a reduction of only 0.94 °C [109]. On average, in tropical regions, deciduous trees reduce the T-air by 2.05 °C, compared to evergreen trees, which achieve an average reduction of 1.86 °C [109].

Additionally, transpiration rates are influenced by weather and climate conditions, with plants actively regulating stomatal openings to manage heat stress and water loss [35,110]. Prolonged heat waves and drought conditions can reduce the effectiveness of evaporative cooling [35,111] and may cause vegetation to release carbon dioxide into the atmosphere [112]. Urban vegetation also provides shading, which intercepts solar radiation, limits heat absorption, and minimizes heat re-radiation via urban surfaces (Figure 1) [105,106]. Shading effectiveness depends on factors like leaf size and density and canopy density [113,114]. Additionally, green spaces modify local wind patterns, facilitating convective heat exchange and dissipating heat flux, further enhancing the cooling effects [79]. In this context, studies in the literature suggest that the dispersed arrangement of tree canopies may be more effective [115,116], additionally preventing heat retention and maintaining optimal relative humidity levels, especially at night [35]. Moreover, vegetation indirectly assists climate cooling by filtering pollutants through dry deposition and pollutant absorption [35], thus reducing urban particulate matter concentration levels by up to 4% [117]. These processes reduce atmospheric scattering and the absorption of radiation, impacting the radiation balance and T-air [118]. Considering the wide range of microclimatic benefits associated with vegetation, GI is the most reliable ecosystem re-source for providing cooling capabilities.

There are fewer studies on the cooling benefits of BI compared to green space, focusing primarily on daytime temperature effects and LST differences, which may not fully capture the conversion of sensible heating to latent heating [35,119]. BI can reduce the daily UHI effect due to water's high heat capacity and low thermal conductivity, as well as evaporation properties, leading to the so-called "thermostatic effect" [79,120]. Shading, reflectance, and thermal inertia play significant roles in BI cooling [79,103], with wind velocity enhancing convective heat transfer and evaporation rates [121]. Dynamic water bodies like rivers carry heat downstream, affecting local temperatures by up to 1.5 °C regarding the mean level of daytime cooling [122], while static water bodies like lakes exhibit thermal stratification, with larger bodies cooling their surroundings by up to 2.4 °C (1 °C more compared to smaller ones) [79,123]. Despite the importance of BI in regulating the urban microclimate, it can, under certain conditions, enhance the nocturnal UHI [123].

Comparative assessments of green space- and blue space-integrated cooling abilities are rare in climate studies. Some research indicates significant cooling effects within street canyons with access to riparian greenery, while also showing variability in cooling potential based on factors such as river water temperature, incident solar radiation, wind speed, and relative humidity [122]. Riparian vegetation has been shown to reduce the net radiation balance and T-air over streams by up to 4 °C [124]. However, vegetation can create windbreaks, promoting moisture accumulation above water surfaces, which may lead to the formation of warm, humid pockets in the "quiet zone" downwind, negatively impacting cooling efficiency in some cases [125]. However, vegetation can only thrive if it has adequate access to water. It is therefore beneficial to integrate GI with BI.

4.2. Local-Scale Properties of BGI Affecting Cooling Potential

Studies on the extent of UCI most frequently identify BGI size [39,126–129], vegetation intensity and quality [130–133] (with grasslands showing the weakest efficiency [46]), adequate irrigation [38,46,134], proportion of forest vegetation [45], and the presence of surface water within BGI boundaries [46,135–137] as the features most strongly influencing the UCI extent provided by BGI in local scale. A key factor influencing the overall cooling effect may also be surface roughness, which depends on vegetation arrangements and affects ventilation characteristics [35]. Larger BGIs can create greater temperature and humidity contrasts, by up to 5–7 °C, with built-up areas, enhancing the park-breeze effect [35,38,76,106,112,138]. Foliage and vegetation conditions may enhance cooling effects by (1) enhancing evaporative cooling [74,102,139] due to intensified photosynthesis [35,111], (2) reducing solar radiation absorption due to shading [106,113,140], and (3) boosting convective cooling, by raising canopy surface roughness [35,79]. Better efficiency in areas integrating green space with water may result from the synergistic capabilities of evaporative cooling and reduced solar radiation absorption by BI through shading by vegetation, which, along with internal convection processes and water mixing in reservoirs, further enhances BI's ability to absorb surrounding heat [35]. Additionally, the proximity of BI usually ensures better access to groundwater, thus strengthening the resilience of GI to drought and increasing the cooling capacity of vegetation [107,110,111].

The complexity of BGI shapes can either positively [63–67] or negatively [44,46,62,68,69] impact the cooling range, depending on the adopted scale [62], climatic zone, and type of development. This complexity can strengthen the cooling effects of vegetation located at the boundary of complexly shaped BGI areas by minimizing thermal stress, leading to stomatal closure [35,140], which can be dependent on surrounding development settings. In dense urban cores, complex BGI shapes can fragment heat-retaining artificial materials, improving local cooling. Conversely, compact development adjacent to a compact BGI areas can lead to increased thermal stress on vegetation at the boundaries due to heat transfer from built-up areas [141]. However, compact shapes may enable more effective cooling distribution through enhanced gradients of temperature and humidity [119]. The complexity of larger BGI areas can also alter the nature of adjacent urban developments, whereby highly intricate BGI shapes often preclude direct adjacency to compact development, as the development becomes dispersed by the branching of BGI areas. This necessitates assessing the impact of shape at a more localized level, with attention to specific configurations, such as circular, orthogonal, or elongated forms. The orientation of these shapes relative to their surroundings is also crucial. For instance, elongated BGI areas aligned parallel to prevailing wind directions within street ventilation corridors are particularly effective, as they enable the more efficient transport of cooled air produced by evapotranspiration and shading [142].

Additionally, the efficiency of surface water compared to vegetation remains a topic of debate [143,144]—it may be greater in terms of LST [60–62,67,145] and lower in terms of T-air [57–60]. Regarding BI, the size and shape also influence its cooling efficiency, with larger bodies with less complex shapes generally providing more significant cooling [61,62,146]. Latitude, seasonal, and diurnal variations also affect the cooling intensity, which is stronger in lower latitudes and varies throughout the day and year [122,147,148].

The spatial configuration and composition may also influence the UCI intensity [149,150]. BGI objects situated in the highest spatial density may interact with their neighboring facilities, limiting each other's cooling zones [129,151,152], which demonstrates the collective cooling capabilities of small, spatially concentrated BGIs. However, while the decentralization of BGI may be more effective in cooling low-density built areas, high-density built areas may require centralized large-scale BGI objects to effectively form

UCI [153]. In this context, the characteristics of BGI objects can also be examined in terms of landscape metrics, where the most significant feature may be the level of aggregation and connectivity of BGI objects [72,154]. Additionally, the combination of edge density and patch density may exert a high influence on UCI [150]. Spatial arrangement has also proven to be important in case of BI, with large water bodies presenting a higher cooling effect compared to equally distributed small water bodies [123].

The examples of the discussed characteristics, along with precise cooling values, are presented in Sections 5.1.3, 5.2.3 and 5.3. Cooling potential values are generally highest for remote sensing-based methods and lowest for numerical simulations. However, as these approaches examine different phenomena, direct comparisons are not advisable. Nonetheless, general trends in significant features influencing BGI cooling potential can be observed, enabling the identification of characteristics with the highest confidence in their effectiveness.

4.3. Urban Morphology Impact

The cooling potential of BGI is influenced not only by its internal characteristics but also by the surrounding urban areas morphology [66,121,129,155]. Through the modification of airflow, atmospheric heat transport, radiation balances, albedo, moisture availability, and surface heating potential [156], the built environment affects evaporative [74,102,139] and convective cooling [35,79], regulating the intensity of the so-called park-breeze effect [35,76,106], which allows the transfer of cooler air to built-up areas due to the temperature difference between the BGI and the urban surfaces (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Diagram of the park-breeze effect mechanism. The arrows and ellipses schematically represent the movement of air masses. Blue arrows indicate air cooled by BGI, while red ones represent air heated by urban structures. The orange dotted line schematically represents vertical cross-section of temperature. Based on Gunawardena et al. [35].

The primary factors through which building types influence the BGI cooling potential are air humidity and temperature contrasts, which regulate the intensity of the park-breeze effect [35,76,106]. These mechanisms are most prominent in the hottest areas of dense central city residential and commercial zones, as well as in large industrial developments [141]. Urban structures also modify wind conditions, affecting the strength of convective cooling on a micro scale and altering urban ventilation corridors effectiveness on a macro scale [157,158]. Strategic tree planting should therefore target the city's hottest areas and streets parallel to wind directions, which can also enhance particulate matter deposition and improve the overall cooling efficiency. Buildings can also influence turbulence intensity

and modify the distribution of heat in their surroundings, altering the strength of local BGI cooling sources [159]. Additionally, urban development can induce thermal stress on plants, potentially leading to stomatal closure and limiting evaporative cooling during extreme temperatures [74,104,158], and can also impact drought risk, which reduces BGI cooling efficiency [74,160,161]. Denser building patterns may thus enhance the park-breeze effect cooling [107,158,162,163], as well as increase plant thermal stress and limit water access, ultimately diminishing cooling potential. However, some studies found that BGI areas adjacent to more intensive urban developments can cool the surrounding area by up to 393 m further and 10 °C more effectively [141], highlighting the dominant influence of advective mechanisms. To enhance this, in the most intensely developed areas, where elevated T-air and poor water conditions prevail, efforts should focus on mitigating thermal stress on vegetation and enhancing its health. Key actions include selecting species tolerant to harsh urban conditions with high LAI, such as *Platanus acerifolia* or *Tilia cordata*, improving soil quality, and acquiring land to establish greenery with complex boundary geometries to reduce extreme T-air contrasts [141]. Complementary measures include introducing micro-scale BGI solutions, such as green roofs and tree lines alongside larger greenery areas to limit heat stress on plants, as well as unsealing ground surfaces under tree canopies to enhance water infiltration and retention to boost cooling by amplifying vegetation health [141]. Where space is limited in dense urban cores, creating new green spaces rather than expanding existing ones is recommended, as the latter may have already reached their maximum cooling capacity [60].

In addition to development patterns, the impact of urban morphology can also be revealed through interactions between individual BGI facilities and the overall BGI layout. For instance, proximity to other vegetated areas or water bodies may reduce evaporative cooling through increased air humidity and reduce the park-breeze effect through decreased T-air contrasts [35]. Conversely, high-density BGI spaces with lush vegetation can alleviate thermal stress on plants [140,164] and enhance soil conditions, thereby improving overall cooling. However, larger BGIs with dense tree canopies, while locally efficient, may also obstruct urban ventilation corridors, potentially reducing city-scale cooling effectiveness. Therefore, ventilation corridor analyses are essential to ensure tall greenery does not obstruct airflow. However, in already poorly ventilated downtown areas, dense vegetation should be prioritized to create stronger temperature gradients that induce the park-breeze effect. These considerations highlight the importance of considering urban morphology in BGI cooling studies.

The most comprehensive model for classifying urban morphology in terms of characteristics relevant to BGI cooling capabilities (e.g., emissivity, reflectivity, conductivity, absorptivity, and sensible heat storage) is the local climate zones (LCZs) classification system developed by Stewart and Oke [156]. This model enables the delineation of homogeneous urban areas based on surface structure and cover, building types, materials, and human activity. LCZs have a distinct screen-height temperature regime, particularly noticeable over dry surfaces during calm nights in areas with uniform landform [156]. In addition to screen-height temperature, LCZs also define homogeneous zones by air humidity regime [165] and local-scale urban ventilation performance [166], thus distinguishing urban spaces by their actual potential for BGI evaporative and convective cooling. Notably, initially designed to define UBL UHIs more accurately [156,167,168], due to the consistent delimitation of homogeneous areas in terms of natural and artificial materials (like emissivity, reflectivity, conductivity, absorptivity, and sensible heat storage capacity), LCZs can also be successfully applied in LST-based studies [48,169–174].

By understanding the various cooling mechanisms of BGI tailored to LCZs, urban planning can be optimized to address specific local needs. BGI interventions should primar-

ily target densely urbanized zones, such as compact high-rise and mid-rise areas, which are particularly susceptible to HWs due to amplified UHI effects and high population densities.

4.4. Potential Negative Effects of BGI

Despite the undeniable benefits of BGI, it is important to highlight potential negative effects and actions that should be avoided. In urban conditions during HWs and droughts, vegetation emits more biogenic volatile organic compounds (BVOCs), which may contribute to warming [175]. BVOCs emissions are categorized into constitutive emissions, such as isoprene, that are continuously produced by plants, and induced emissions that are triggered by HWs, elevated ozone, and oxidative stress. These compounds play a crucial role in the formation of secondary organic aerosols (SOAs), which affect aerosol–cloud interactions and the concentrations of ozone and methane in a feedback process [176]. While SOAs can cool the atmosphere by altering cloud properties, ozone and methane exacerbate warming by absorbing thermal radiation, further influencing BVOC emissions [177]. Additionally, SOA can contribute to particulate matter increase, amplifying the UHI. Therefore, the impact on climate—whether cooling or warming—depends on the balance of positive (increased albedo and carbon fixation) and negative (greenhouse gas emissions) feedback [178]. Importantly, the magnitude of BVOC emissions is also influenced by direct factors such as leaf metabolism and indirect factors like ecosystem structure, species composition, and biomass [178]. Considering that, in cities, BVOCs can increase by 5–14% (for organic matter) and lead to a 1.0–2.4% increase in ozone concentrations during HWs [179], it is crucial to implement countermeasures to mitigate environmental stress. Mitigation strategies should focus on selecting stress-resilient plant species, enhancing biodiversity, optimizing vegetation placement to prevent pollutant stagnation, enhancing soil conditions and retention, and ensuring adequate irrigation and drought mitigation practices.

Additionally, it is essential to align BGI with the nature-based solutions (NBSs) concept [180]. Otherwise, BGI may harm biodiversity and habitat quality if inappropriate plant species, such as invasive ones, are chosen. This issue can also arise when species sensitive to urban conditions are chosen, as they may require excessive irrigation. Selecting native, drought-resistant species that need less water is consistent with NBS and more beneficial. Furthermore, protecting existing vegetation, including unmanaged areas and ruderal plants, should take priority over creating new green spaces on unsuitable land. Another risk of misaligning BGI with NBS is the improper use of hydrological engineering solutions, such as green roofs and walls. The environmental and economic costs of irrigation for such solutions may outweigh their cooling benefits, especially during droughts. Using NBS-related climbing plants that draw water from native soil, rather than more water-intensive solutions like modular green walls, can be more effective. However, it is important to design systems that do not interfere with building facades, as this could lead to increased costs during future repairs. Furthermore, the NBS-related issue extends to infiltration systems, which have the potential to drain adjacent areas, thereby depleting soil moisture, reducing water retention, and exacerbating drought risks. Consequently, hydrological engineering solutions should prioritize water retention, interception, and gradual release into the soil, as opposed to rapid drainage.

5. Characteristics of Selected Geoinformatics Methods and Spatial Data Used to Assess the Cooling Potential of BGI

5.1. UCI Studies Based on Satellite Remote Sensing

The remote sensing approach is based on LST. These data are typically obtained through satellite remote sensing using passive sensors that detect both shortwave radiation reflected from the land surface and emitted longwave (thermal infrared) radiation [181].

5.1.1. Methods for Creating BGI Representation

In remote sensing studies, two primary types of BGI representation are distinguished: continuous and discrete. Continuous BGI representation is achieved through vegetation indices, such as the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), which illustrate the spatial distribution and intensity of BGI presence. In this study, each raster pixel is treated as an individual sample, making the analysis of BGI efficiency largely based on correlating the BGI raster with the LST raster [182]. Discrete representation, on the other hand, involves clearly defined boundaries for BGI areas, facilitating differentiation between vegetation and surface water [63]. However, accurately delineating BGI boundaries can be challenging. Common methods include supervised classification and reclassification of vegetation indices (e.g., NDVI); in this model, each BGI feature is treated as a single sample. Additionally, the method facilitates the use of predefined urban data (e.g., only publicly accessible green spaces). In SUHI analyses, less common representation methods have also emerged offering unique advantages, such as the “cooling network and cooling source areas” model, which organizes information on BGI features through morphological spatial pattern analysis (MSPA) [149].

5.1.2. Methods for Assessing the Cooling Potential of BGI

The cooling extent directly influenced by BGI is challenging to evaluate, as it depends on both BGI characteristics and the thermal conditions of adjacent built-up areas [151,183]. Common approaches focus on identifying the first turning point in the LST-distance function from the edge of a BGI feature [63,68,145,160,184,185]. This approach mainly aims to define the cooling range or cooling distance of BGI (HCD), which ends at the first inflection point on the function, and cooling intensity (HCI), measured as the LST difference between the first turning point and the BGI boundary. Calculating these indicators typically involves various spatial analyses, with popular methods including the assessment of LST increase based on zonal means in buffer zones around BGI features [70,160]. LST values can also be collected along straight lines extending outward from BGI boundaries, in cross-sections [63], to evaluate potential variations in UCI extent direction. More advanced techniques like the semivariance function [151,186] or the use of watershed algorithms that treat LST as the terrain elevation, where watersheds represent cooling zones, are also applied [129]. Surface-based methods are most effective, as they capture directional cooling influences, though validation against control measurements is essential for accuracy.

5.1.3. Remote Sensing Data Used in UCI Studies

The most commonly used data sources for LST calculations include the Landsat satellite series, the MODIS instrument, and ASTER [48]. The capability for thermal radiation detection began in 1982 with the launch of the thematic mapper (TM) sensor on the Landsat 4 satellite, which imaged the Earth’s surface via thermal infrared remote sensing at a spatial resolution of 120 m [187]. The latest generations of Landsat (8 and 9) can generate LST data using the thermal infra-red sensor (TIRS), which has a resolution of 100 m, with the possibility of resampling to 30 m to match the bands of the Operational Land Imager (OLI) [188]. Since 2008, Landsat data have been freely available with a single image covering an area of 185×185 km, allowing for the analysis of entire urban areas based on data from a single time point. For Landsat 5, 7, 8, and 9, the revisit cycle for the same area is 16 days, with Landsat 8 and 9 having revisit schedules that enable the temporal resolution to be increased to 8 days. This facilitates the analysis of UCI changes over time with high frequency, enabling the impact of land use changes on urban thermal conditions to be recorded. Landsat is therefore one of the most effective sources of information on the thermal characteristics of urban areas.

The second most popular source of LST data is MODIS, an instrument mounted on the Terra and Aqua satellites [48,189–191], which were launched in 1999 and 2002. The temporal resolution of MODIS data is 1–2 days, facilitating the creation of high-frequency time series, but the spatial resolution is only 1 km, limiting the ability to conduct detailed analyses of the cooling potential of individual BGI objects. However, due to the large size of each image (a 2330 km wide strip), MODIS is widely used in studies of large areas [48,192,193]. Additionally, MODIS provides many ready-to-use products, including daytime and nighttime LST and emissivity data [194,195], which are freely available.

Another source of LST data is ASTER, located on the Terra satellite [48,196]. These data were collected during the radiometer's operational period from 1999 to 2016. ASTER imaged the Earth's surface in 14 bands, with 4 of them capturing the thermal infrared spectrum at a spatial resolution of 90 m [197]. This instrument provided access to the surface kinetic temperature product, available for both daytime and nighttime [48,198]. Like Landsat and MODIS, ASTER data are also freely available, but are rarely used in studies of UCI extent.

In recent years, LST data from the ECOSystem Spaceborne Thermal Radiometer Experiment on Space Station (ECOSTRESS) sensor have gained increasing popularity [56,199,200]. This sensor was launched to the International Space Station (ISS) on 29 June 2018, with a temporal repeat cycle of 3–5 days, depending on the latitude [201]. ECOSTRESS images the Earth's surface in five bands, providing LST with a spatial resolution of 38 m × 68 m, with a single image covering an area of 402 km (53°) [56]. The main advantage of ECOSTRESS data is the inclined, precessing ISS orbit, which facilitates imaging the same area at different times of the day and night, thus enabling analysis of diurnal variations [201]. Additionally, the five channels enable more accurate multispectral temperature emissivity separation (TES) approaches for LST calculations [56,202]. ECOSTRESS data are also freely available, though due to the relatively recent launch of ECOSTRESS, these data have not yet been used to study the thermal effectiveness of BGI characteristics.

Additional useful data for BGI research include the following: PlanetScope SuperDove (free for research purposes, 3 m resolution, eight bands, ideal for time-series BGI and vegetation health classification); WorldView (paid, up to 0.3 m resolution, 16 bands, excellent for BGI and artificial materials classification); IKONOS, QuickBird, GeoEye-1, Pleiades-1, SPOT-5/6/7, Gaofen, and SkySat (effective for BGI classification); Prisma (30 m hyperspectral data for vegetation species classification); EnMap (high-resolution hyperspectral data); Sentinel-5P (free, suitable for air pollution time-series mapping); Sentinel-2 (free, good for large-scale BGI classification and vegetation health assessments); and ERA5 (free, high-temporal-resolution weather model).

Examples of research results on BGI features affecting its cooling potential using remote sensing techniques are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Examples of studies on BGI features affecting its cooling efficiency using satellite remote sensing (+ and – indicate the direction of the feature’s influence on cooling potential; the multiplicity of the sign indicates the relative significance of the influence).

Source	Satellite Sensor	LST Spatial Resolution	LST Retrieval Method	Date and Temporal Resolution	Study Region	BGI Type	Cooling Potential Calculation Method	Cooling Potential Values	Method for Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	Most Efficient BGI Characteristics
Sun et al. [70]	ASTER	15 m from 90 m	TES	daytime; 8 August 2007; 16 days	Beijing, China	Wetlands (15 objects)	HCD: mean LST in 50 m buffer rings; HCI: temperature difference between HCDmin and HCDmax	HCDmax: 2500 m; HCDmean: 963 m; HCImax: 5.83 °C; HCImean: 2.6 °C	Spearman rank correlation coefficient	Area, LSI, perimeter-area ratio (PARA), path-fractal dimension (PFD), distance to the city center (DCC)	Area HCD (+); HCI (–) LSI HCD (–); HCI (–) DCC HCD (+); HCI (–)
Shah et al. [203]	Landsat 8 TIRS	30 m from 100 m	The mono-window algorithm (MW)	daytime; 24 April 2017; 2 January 2017	Bengaluru, India	Green spaces (manually traced based on Google Earth) (262 objects)	HCD: mean LST in 30 m buffer rings; HCI: temperature difference between BGI object border and HCDmax	HCDmean: 347 m; HCImean: 2.23 °C	Multiple linear regression model	Area, LSI, NDVI of BGI, NDVI of buffer	LSI HCD (+) NDVI of BGI HCD (+)
Zhang et al. [160]	Landsat 8 (LST) LocaSpace Viewer (BGI)	100 m	The radiative transfer equation method (RTE)	daytime; 2 August 2021; 16 days	Xi’an, China	Comprehensive, ecological, theme and belt parks (40 objects)	HCD: mean LST in 25 m buffer rings; HCI: temperature difference between BGI mean LST and HCDmax; park cold island efficiency (PCE), intensity (PCI), gradient (PCG)	HCImax: 4.44 °C; HCImean: 2.22 °C	Pearson correlation coefficient	Composition: area, perimeter, water area, green area, impermeable surface area; Configuration: park shape index, patch density, edge density	Area HCI (++) Perimeter HCI (+) Water area HCI (+) Green area HCI (++) PCI (+) Park shape index HCI (+); PCI (+) Patch density PCE (+) Edge density PCE (+)
Garcia-Haro et al. [204]	Landsat 8 TIRS	30 m from 100 m	The emissivity corrected algorithm (EC)	21 June 2017; 24 June 2018; 20 June 2019; 22 June 2020	Barcelona, Spain	Urban parks (86 objects)	HCD: mean LST in 10 m buffer rings; HCI: temperature difference between BGI mean LST and HCDmax	HCDmean: 91.98 m; HCDmax: 280 m; HCImean: 1.84 °C; HCImax: 3.74 °C	Bivariate correlation and multiple linear regression analysis	Size LSI, proportion of green land cover, greenery composition, urban surrounding characteristics	Greenery composition (+) Greenery area (+) Area (+/–) LSI (–)

Table 1. Cont.

Source	Satellite Sensor	LST Spatial Resolution	LST Retrieval Method	Date and Temporal Resolution	Study Region	BGI Type	Cooling Potential Calculation Method	Cooling Potential Values	Method for Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	Most Efficient BGI Characteristics
Qiu et al. [63]	Landsat 8 TIRS and Landsat 5 TM	30 m from 100/120 m	N/A	daytime; 23 August 1998, 21 August 2009, 17 August 2019; 16 days	Changsha, China	Green spaces (53 objects) and blue spaces (28 objects)	HCD: LST sampling on eight straight lines from BGI object; HCI: temperature difference between BGI object border and HCDmax	HCDGI _{max} : 340 m; HCDGI _{mean} : 163.33 m; HCIGI _{max} : 3.54 °C; HCIGI _{mean} : 1.8 °C; HCDBI _{max} : 370 m; HCDBI _{mean} : 175.58 m; HCIBI _{max} : 5.04 °C; HCIBI _{mean} : 2 °C	Logarithmic regression analysis; nonlinear surface fitting	Area, LSI	Area (+) LSI (+)
Bao et al. [151]	Landsat 8 TIRS and Landsat 5 TM	30 m from 100/120 m	MW	daytime; 2000, 2004, 2007, 2011, 2014	Baotou, Mongolia	Green spaces (screen visual interpretation) (9 objects)	HCD: semi-variance function	HCD: 1600 m	Linear and nonlinear regression	Class Area (CA), Number of Patches (NP), LSI, Aggregation Index (AI), Shannon's Evenness Index (SHEI), Mean Patch Fractal Dimension (FRAC_MN), PARA, NDVI	Area (++) NDVI (+)
Yu et al. [46]	Landsat 7 TM and Landsat 8 TIRS SPOT5 (for BGI classification)	30 m from 120/100 m	RTE	daytime; 23 July 2000, 4 April 2013	Fuzhou, China	BGI (106 BGI and 329 GI (280 tree-based and 49 grass-based))	HCD: mean LST in 30 m buffer rings; HCI: temperature difference between BGI object border and HCDmax; cooling efficiency (HCE); Threshold value of efficiency (TVoE)	HCD _{mean} : 104 m; HCI _{mean} : 1.78 °C; TVoE: 4.55 ha	Linear regression and hierarchical cluster analysis for dividing BGI into size-based groups	Area, LSI, fractal dimension index (FRAC), water body presence	Area (+) Waterbody presence (+) LSI (-)
Xue et al. [205]	Landsat 8 TIRS	30 m from 100 m	The split-window algorithm (SW)	daytime; 4 July 2016	Changchun City, China	Wetlands (21 objects)	HCD: mean LST in 50 m buffer rings; cooling capability index (CCI); normalized CCI; cooling efficiency index (CEI), normalized CEI	HCD _{max} : 1000 m; HCD _{mean} : 371.1 m; HCI _{mean} : 2.74 °C	Spearman's Rho Correlations	Area, LSI, hydrologic connectivity, type (rivers, lakes, wetlands, green spaces)	Area (++) LSI (+) Connectivity (+) Type: lakes (+)

Table 1. Cont.

Source	Satellite Sensor	LST Spatial Resolution	LST Retrieval Method	Date and Temporal Resolution	Study Region	BGI Type	Cooling Potential Calculation Method	Cooling Potential Values	Method for Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	Most Efficient BGI Characteristics
Du H. et al. [66]	Landsat 8 TIRS	30 m from 100 m	RTE	daytime; 29 August 2013	Shanghai, China	Green spaces (manually traced based on Google Earth)	HCD: mean LST in 10 m buffer rings; HCI: temperature difference between BGI object border and HCDmax	HCDmean: 570 m; HCDmax: 1610 m HCImean: 2.63 °C HCImax: 9.35 °C	Curve fitting and Pearson correlation coefficient	Area, LSI, percentage of vegetation, percentage of water body	Area (+) LSI (+) Percentage of water body inside the green space (+)
Cao et al. [206]	ASTER	90 m	TES	10 July 2000, 30 October 2003, 25 May 2004	Nagoya, Japan	Urban parks (92 objects)	HCI: difference in temperature inside the park and the average temperature in the buffer 500 m from the park	HCImax: 6.82 °C; HCImean: 1.3 °C	Multivariate regression	Area, LSI, grass area, water area, shrubs area	Area (+) Grass area (-) LSI (-)
Lin et al. [129]	Landsat 5 TM	35 m from 120 m	MW	daytime; 22 September 2009	Beijing, China	Green areas (NDVI reclassification) (30 objects)	HCD, HCI, and cooling area (CA): based on watershed algorithm geometry	HCDmax: 840 m; HCImean: 2.3–4.8 °C; CAmax: 10.09 km ²	Nonlinear regression T-Student's test	Area	Area HCD (+) HCI (+) CA (++)
Zhao et al. [207]	Landsat 8 TIRS and MODIS-Terra	Landsat 8: 30 m MODIS: 250 m	N/A	2015	Xiamen, China	Vegetation surfaces	Average temperature reduction (T-air) Hourly heat absorption (MJ/a)	1.28 °C 2.04×10^9 MJ/a	N/A	Vegetation type	Needleleaf forest, broadleaf forest, and mixed forest (+)
Nasar-u-Minallah et al. [154]	Landsat 8 TIRS and Landsat 5 TM	30 m from 100/120 m	N/A	2000, 2010, 2020	Lahore, Pakistan	Urban green spaces and impervious surfaces (built-up areas)	LST reduction	3 °C	Correlation analysis	Percentage of the landscape (PLAND), patch density (PD), class area (CA), largest patch index (LPI), number of patches (NP), aggregation index (AI), LSI, patch richness (PR), and mean patch shape index (SHAPE_MN)	Aggregation of patches (++) PLAND (+) CA (+) LPI (+) Size (+) Shape complexity (+)

Table 1. Cont.

Source	Satellite Sensor	LST Spatial Resolution	LST Retrieval Method	Date and Temporal Resolution	Study Region	BGI Type	Cooling Potential Calculation Method	Cooling Potential Values	Method for Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	Most Efficient BGI Characteristics
Verma et al. [72]	Landsat 8 TIRS; PlanetScope	3 m from 100 m (downscaled via PlanetScope NDVI)	RTE/SW	16 April 2020	Lucknow, India	Urban parks	R2 of LST and BGI features in 3/6/30/60 m buffers function	HCI: 2.55 °C HCD: 18 m	Regression analysis	Area, core area index (CAI), related circumscribing circle (CIRCLE), contiguity index (CONTIG), core area (CORE), Euclidean nearest neighbor distance (ENN), FRAC, radius of gyration (GYRATE), number of core areas (NCORE), PARA, patch perimeter (PERIM), shape index (SHAPE)	CONTIG (+) CAI (+) FRAC (+) PARA (+)

5.2. UCI Studies Based on Numerical Simulations

The most effective approach for modeling the cooling potential of BGI is CFD models due to their ability to simulate dynamic changes in system elements [96]. CFD produces quantitative predictions of fluid-flow phenomena based on the conservation laws (conservation of mass, momentum, and energy) governing fluid motion [95]. CFD models are based on interactions between urban fabric elements and local atmospheric parameters. These simulations account for shortwave and longwave radiation influx and outflux, anthropogenic heat, energy storage in artificial materials, evaporation, and heat exchange and transport by wind [208]. CFD results differ from remote sensing studies mainly due to limited computational capacity, which hinders the comprehensive study of large-scale characteristics like surface area, shape complexity, and the spatial configuration of larger BGI areas. Numerical simulations usually focus on smaller-scale BGI elements like tree groves, lawns, and green roofs and walls.

One of the most effective CFD models for BGI analysis is ENVI-met, designed to simulate surface–plant–air interactions in urban environments [96,100,209,210] and daily climate cycles [210]. ENVI-met is a three-dimensional microclimate model based on a voxel grid, using Reynolds Averaged Navier–Stokes equations for wind flow and an indexed view sphere scheme for radiative fluxes [96]. ENVI-met comprises several sub-models: a 1D boundary model for atmospheric conditions; a 3D atmospheric model for simulating temperature, humidity, turbulence, radiation, and pollutants; a soil model for temperature and humidity fluxes; and a vegetation model for transpiration, leaf temperature, and plant–atmosphere interactions. The simulation requires two input files: one defining area layout (buildings, vegetation, soil) and another with meteorological settings and output parameters.

ENVI-met allows the definition of thermal mass and heat inertia on buildings, as well as diurnal atmospheric boundary conditions (such as T-air and relative humidity) [210,211] from mesoscale meteorological models or field observations [212], enhancing model accuracy [213]. Meteorological settings have the greatest impact on the results, emphasizing the importance of informed initial conditions. Local hourly T-air is recommended as forcing data. Simulating small areas, as 200×200 m, is advised when using local weather data, as domain size can affect wind speed and T-air. While material details mainly influence surface and radiant temperatures, T-air values can be generally uniform across microscale domains. However, wind speed and solar radiation may vary significantly, affecting natural ventilation and building energy demand [214].

Beyond the initial conditions, the accuracy of ENVI-met simulations is also highly sensitive to the choice of lateral boundary conditions (LBCs), including open, closed (forced), and cyclic types, directly influencing airflow dynamics and temperature distribution. Open LBCs minimize boundary influence by copying values from internal grid points to the boundary, making them ideal for large or dynamic domains. However, they can cause numerical instabilities when internal values are not representative. Forced LBCs use boundary values from a 1D model or external data, improving model stability, especially for long-term simulations, but potentially introducing errors if the forcing profile does not reflect the average conditions. In “simple forcing”, only temperature and humidity are forced, while “full forcing” applies to all variables, including wind. Cyclic LBCs assume similar conditions at both boundaries, making them efficient for simulating periodic patterns but potentially unstable when boundary conditions are dissimilar. To optimize simulations, dynamic forcing and open boundaries are recommended for accuracy, while static forcing improves computational efficiency in short-term simulations [215].

The accuracy of numerical simulations can vary depending on proximity to boundaries. Points far from the boundary reflect field accuracy, while accuracy near the boundary

depends on the numerical precision of the boundary conditions [216]. Due to limited knowledge of spatiotemporal variations in boundary thermophysical properties, boundary conditions often rely on assumptions that overlook nearby structures' local effects [53]. A multi-scale coupled approach, incorporating spatially and temporally resolved measurements and urban atmosphere dynamics, can improve boundary condition precision and enhance microscale CFD accuracy [217]. Nested grids, commonly used in weather forecasting [218], can transfer information between larger and smaller domains, but are absent in tools like ENVI-met. Alternatively, a buffer zone can be employed, sized to ensure stability in the domain's solution [219].

Despite its advancements, ENVI-met still has some limitations, including issues with radiation flux calculations, turbulence modeling which tends to overestimate the turbulent production in high acceleration areas, the grid generation, lack of information about near-wall phenomena, the inability to fully account for atmospheric flow characteristics, and the assumption of constant cloudiness and wind conditions [96,220–223].

An alternative to the commercial ENVI-met software is Ladybug Tools, which integrates its modules Butterfly and Honeybee. Butterfly is a plugin for Grasshopper/Dynamo and a Python library based on an object-oriented paradigm. It is built on OpenFOAM, an open-source CFD engine capable of running simulations and turbulence models, from simple RAS (Reynolds-averaged simulation) models to more complex LES (large eddy simulation) models [224,225]. Honeybee, on the other hand, supports detailed daylighting and thermodynamics modeling, also being an open Python library. It allows the creation, execution, and visualization of daylighting and radiation simulations using the Radiance engine, as well as energy simulations with EnergyPlus/OpenStudio [224,225].

5.2.1. Methods for Creating BGI Representation

Both OpenFOAM and the Simple Plant Module of ENVI-met use statistical methods to describe vegetation morphology through LAI [97]. ENVI-met also includes a 3D-Plant module, which creates representations of canopy geometry as a mesh that approximates the shape and location of objects, incorporating leaf area density (LAD) and root area density [226]. In addition to aerodynamic characteristics, vegetation has radiation effects, described by transparency that influences the transmission of solar radiation [96–98]. Water bodies are often represented by a specific soil type, partially transparent to shortwave radiation [227], with defined heat conductivity, heat capacity, and depth. Computational processes within the water body model consider the transmission and absorption of shortwave radiation [227]. However, no secondary energy balance or supplementary boundary conditions are applied to the water or ground surfaces. As such, water grids are assumed to be deep enough to absorb most of the shortwave radiation. Some models, like ENVI-met 4.0, also simulate water spray effects, enabling the modeling of fountains and cooling through air–water aerosols [228].

5.2.2. Methods for Assessing the Cooling Potential of BGI

Analyses based on computational fluid dynamics often involve comparing spatial development scenarios in terms of mean T-air or thermal comfort indices for the study area in both baseline and post-BGI implementation conditions, focusing on features such as spatial layout, coverage configuration, and tree density [142,229–232]. Studies assessing the maximum cooling range are rare [142], and evaluations of the area directly affected by BGI's cooling capacity are not typically performed.

In addition to T-air, CFD-based studies can also assess variations in mean radiant temperature (T-mrt), LST [183,211,233–236], and human thermal comfort indices, such as the physiological equivalent temperature (PET) index [211], which depends on T-air,

humidity, wind speed, radiation fluxes, and individual factors like body energy balance, gender, age, weight, and clothing [231]. Another example is the universal thermal climate index (UTCI), which provides an equivalent temperature incorporating T-air, wind speed, humidity, T-mrt, and typical clothing based on weather conditions [237].

5.2.3. Data Used for ENVI-Met Simulation

In ENVI-met, the spatial configuration file must include information on the location, dimensions, and materials of building walls and roofs. Additionally, details about vegetation, surface characteristics, and soil properties in undeveloped areas are required. Spatial parameters can be obtained through remote sensing, significantly reducing field data collection time. High spatial and spectral resolution remote sensing data are needed to ensure model accuracy. The model also requires meteorological parameters such as the wind speed and direction, relative humidity, and surface roughness to initialize the simulation [235]. Table 2 presents the main input parameters required by ENVI-met along with potential data sources.

Table 2. Basic data required to run the ENVI-met model along with data source examples. Based on Heldens et al. [238].

Input Data	Input Parameter	Source Type	Source Examples
Buildings	Location	Remote sensing, cadaster maps, topographic data	PlanetScope, WorldView, QuickBird, IKONOS, ALS point clouds, airborne images, Open Street Map
	Roof material	Remote sensing (hyperspectral)	Airborne hyperspectral imagery (e.g., HyMap)
	Height	Remote sensing, photogrammetry	ALS point clouds, stereo imagery
	Material properties: reflectance properties	Remote sensing (hyperspectral)	Airborne hyperspectral imagery (e.g., HyMap)
	Material properties: thermal inertia	Literature	–
Vegetation	Location	Remote sensing	PlanetScope, WorldView, QuickBird, IKONOS, airborne images, ALS point clouds
	Type (deciduous, coniferous, grass)	Remote sensing	Airborne hyperspectral imagery (e.g., HyMap); PlanetScope, WorldView, QuickBird, IKONOS—only using time-series
	Height	Remote sensing, photogrammetry	ALS DEMs, stereo imagery
	Leaf area density	Remote sensing	Sentinel-2A integrated with ALS DEMs, airborne hyperspectral imagery (e.g., HyMap)
	Photosynthetic and evapotranspiration properties	Literature	–
Non-build surfaces	Location	Remote sensing	PlanetScope, WorldView, QuickBird, IKONOS, airborne images
	Type (impervious, pervious)	Remote sensing	PlanetScope, WorldView, QuickBird, IKONOS, airborne images, airborne hyperspectral imagery (e.g., HyMap)
	Soil properties (hydrological)	Literature	–
Weather conditions	Temperature, relative humidity	Weather station/field measurements	OpenSenseMap, Luftdaten, ERA5
	Wind speed and direction	Weather station/field measurements	OpenSenseMap, Luftdaten, ERA5, Global Wind Atlas
	Date, sun dawn time, sun set time	Location-related variable	–

Examples of research results on BGI characteristics influencing its cooling potential using numerical simulations are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Examples of studies on BGI characteristics influencing its cooling efficiency using numerical simulations (+ and – indicate the direction of the feature’s influence on cooling potential; the multiplicity of the sign indicates the relative significance of the influence).

Source	Model	Study Region	Time of Simulation	BGI Type	Cooling Potential Index	Cooling Potential Values	Method for Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	BGI Most Efficient Characteristics
Vidrih and Medved [239]	Three-dimensional CFD modeling	Ljubljana, Slovenia	July 2013	Urban park	T-air	4.7 °C	Comparing different scenarios	Tree density (LAI), size	Tree density (+)
Skelhorn et al. [183]	ENVI-met	Manchester, UK	13 July 2014	Vegetation, mature trees and new trees	T-air	0–1 °C	Comparing different scenarios	Vegetation fraction, type (mature trees, grassland, hedge, green roof)	Mature tree canopies area fraction (5% → 1 °C peak LST) (+) Hedges fraction (5% → 0.46 °C peak LST) (+) Green roof area fraction (+/–)
Taleghani et al. [234]	ENVI-met	Los Angeles, CA, USA	30–31 July 2014	Street trees, green roofs	T-air, T-mrt, PET	0.2 °C T-air	Comparing six different scenarios	Type (green roof, street trees)	Type: street trees (+)
Ghaffarianhoseini et al. [240]	ENVI-met	Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia	5 March 2013	Trees, grasslands	T-air	3.3 °C	Comparing different scenarios (100% grass, 25% trees, 50% trees, 75% trees)	Location and orientation, dimensions and albedo, wall enclosures, presence of greenery, type (grass, trees)	Tree coverage (++) North and east orientation of courtyard in relation to the development (+)
Lee et al. [211]	ENVI-met	Freiburg, Germany	4 August 2003	Trees, grasslands	PET, T-air, T-mrt	Trees: max 2.7 °C T-air, 39.1 °C T-mrt, 17.4 °C PET; Grasslands: max 3.4 °C T-air, 7.5 °C T-mrt, 4.9 °C PET	Comparing different scenarios	Different types of spatial arrangements of trees and lawns, type (tree, grassland)	Type: trees (++) Vegetation fraction (+)
Morakinyo et al. [233]	ENVI-met with EnergyPlus	Cairo, Egypt; Hong-Kong; Tokyo, Japan; Paris, France	N/A	Green wall, green roof	Indoor T-air, LST	1.4 °C indoor T-air; 14, 10, 8.5, 7 °C LST	Comparing 60 different scenarios	Four types of green roofs	Green roof intensity (thickness of soil and vegetation layer) (+)

Table 3. Cont.

Source	Model	Study Region	Time of Simulation	BGI Type	Cooling Potential Index	Cooling Potential Values	Method for Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	BGI Most Efficient Characteristics
Middel et al. [230]	ENVI-met	Phoenix, AZ, USA	23 June 2011	Trees	T-air (at 2 m)	max 4.4 °C	Comparing 54 different scenarios	Tree canopy area fraction	Tree canopies area fraction (1% → 0.14 °C peak T-air; 10% → 2 °C peak T-air) (+)
Ziaul and Pal [236]	ENVI-met	Malda, India	N/A	Green roofs, green walls	T-air, LST	2.6 °C T-air	Comparing different scenarios (100% green roof; 100% green roof and green wall; 50% green roof and green wall) across different development types	Different configurations of green roofs, green walls, and plantings according to different development types	For open mid-rise and compact low-rise 100% green roof and green wall (2.6 and 1.33 °C peak T-air) For open low-rise 50% green roof and green wall, including planting (1.87 °C peak T-air)
Ng et al. [229]	ENVI-met	Hong Kong, China	9 May 2012	Green spaces (33 different cases)	Reduction in T-air at pedestrian level	0–1.8 °C	Comparing different scenarios	Vegetation fraction, type (trees, grassland, green roof)	Tree canopy area fraction (33% → 1 °C peak T-air) (++) Type: trees (+) Green roof area fraction (+/-)
Lin and Lin [241]	ENVI-met	Taipei, Taiwan	N/A	Urban parks (8 objects)	T-air	max 2.72 °C	Comparing different scenarios	Different types of geometries and spatial arrangements of parks	Area (+) Park number (+) Area of the largest park (+) More regular spatial arrangement (+) Greater diversity of parks (+)

Table 3. Cont.

Source	Model	Study Region	Time of Simulation	BGI Type	Cooling Potential Index	Cooling Potential Values	Method for Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	BGI Most Efficient Characteristics
O'Malley et al. [58]	ENVI-met	London, UK	N/A	Green open spaces (trees, shrubs and grass) and water bodies	T-air	1.12–1.14 °C	Comparing three different scenarios	Type (vegetation, water bodies)	Vegetation (+) Water bodies (+)
Santamouris et al. [242]	ENVI-met with EnergyPlus	Sydney, Australia	N/A	Green pavements, green roofs	T-air, energy conservation (%)	Green pavements: 0.3–1.4 °C T-air; 0.48–2.31% Energy conservation; Green roofs: 0.5 °C T-air	Comparing three different mitigation strategies (20, 40, 60% vegetation fraction)	Green pavement fraction; green roof fraction	Green pavement fraction (20% → 0.3 °C peak T-air; 60% → 1.4 °C peak T-air) (+)
Wang et al. [231]	ENVI-met	Toronto, ON, Canada	15 January 2013 and 15 July 2013	Urban vegetation	T-air, T-mrt	Max 0.8 °C T-air	Comparing different scenarios	Urban vegetation fraction within 3 types of built-up areas	Urban vegetation area fraction (10% → 0.8 °C peak T-air, 8.3 °C peak T-mrt) (+)
Declat-Barreto et al. [235]	ENVI-met	Phoenix, AZ, USA	16–17 July 2005	Trees and grass	T-air, LST	0.9–1.9 °C T-air; 0.8–8.4 °C LST	Comparing baseline and green scenario	Greenery fraction	Greenery fraction (+)
Salata et al. [243]	ENVI-met	Rome, Italy	16 July 2014	Green open spaces	T-air, Mediterranean Outdoor Comfort Index (MOCI)	1.34 °C T-air; 2.5–3.5 MOCI	Comparing six different scenarios	Increase in vegetation fraction by 9%	Vegetation fraction (+)
Herath et al. [232]	ENVI-met	Colombo, Sri Lanka	29–30 August 2016	Green roof, green wall	T-air	Green roof: 1.76–1.9 °C	Comparing six different scenarios (trees in curbsides, green roofing 100%/50%, green walls 50%, combined)	Type (green roofs, green walls, trees in curbsides)	Combined types (trees, 50% green roofs, 50% green walls) (+++) 50% green walls (++) 100% green roofs (+)

Table 3. Cont.

Source	Model	Study Region	Time of Simulation	BGI Type	Cooling Potential Index	Cooling Potential Values	Method for Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	BGI Most Efficient Characteristics
Zhao et al. [116]	ENVI-met	Tempe, AZ, USA	13 June 2017	Trees	T-air, PET, wind speed	0.19 °C T-air 0.9 °C PET	Comparing nine different scenarios	Tree density/layout	Equal interval trees layout (with effective ventilation) T-air: (++) Wind speed: (+/-) Overlapping clustered trees layout T-air: (+) Wind speed: (-) No trees T-air (-) Wind speed: (++)
Cao et al. [146]	ENVI-met	Beijing, China	31 July 2018	Urban water bodies	T-air all-day cooling effect	1.57 °C	Comparing different scenarios	Water fraction, separation index (SI), LSI, waterfront green space type	Water fraction (64% → max cooling) (+) LSI (+) SI (threshold) (+) GI type: trees (+)
Berardi et al. [142]	ENVI-met, WRF-UCM	Toronto, ON, Canada	3–5 July 2018	Green roofs, trees	HCI, HCD (T-air); HTCI	ENVI-met: HCI: 0.5–1.4 °C HCD: 250 m HTCI: 0.3–1.2 °C maxHTCI: 11 °C WRF-UCM: HCI: 0.8–2 °C	Comparing two different scenarios (50, 80%)	Green roof fraction, LAD, leaf shortwave transmittance, spatial arrangement of trees	Vegetation fraction (++) LAD (++) Leaf shortwave transmittance (++) Planting trees along street canyons located parallel to the wind direction (+)

Table 3. Cont.

Source	Model	Study Region	Time of Simulation	BGI Type	Cooling Potential Index	Cooling Potential Values	Method for Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	BGI Most Efficient Characteristics
Mohammed et al. [244]	WRF with SLUCM	Dubai, UAE	January, July 2019	GI	Ambient temperature	1.7 °C	Comparing different scenarios (25, 50, 75, 100%)	Greenery fraction	Greenery fraction (+)
Sharma et al. [245]	WRF with SLUCM	Chicago Metropolitan Area, IL, USA	16–18 August 2013	Green roofs	LST	3.41 °C for roofs; ~7 °C for core urban area	Comparing different scenarios (25, 50, 75, 100%)	Green roof fraction	Green roof fraction (+)
Khan et al. [246]	WRF with SLUCM	Kolkata, India	6–8 April 2020	Green roofs	Ambient temperature	0.9 °C	Comparing different scenarios (25, 50, 75, 100%)	Green roof fraction	Green roof fraction (+)
Haddad et al. [247]	WRF	Riyadh, Saudi Arabia	2016–2020	Irrigated/non-irrigated GI	Ambient temperature	Irrigated: 2.1 °C; Non-irrigated: 0.8 °C	Comparing different scenarios (20–60% irrigated/non-irrigated)	Greenery fraction, irrigation	Greenery fraction (+) Irrigation (+)
Khan et al. [248]	WRF	Athens, Greece	N/A	GI	T-air	0.7–1.1 °C	Comparing three different scenarios (30, 50, 70%)	Greenery fraction	Greenery fraction (+)

5.3. UCI Studies Based on Field Measurements

In field measurements of UCI, evaluation of cooling effects can be performed through T-air and other atmospheric parameter measurements, either stationary or using mobile sensors. Typically, characteristics like LAI, vegetation height, and crown density are examined in relation to meteorological conditions and their bioclimatic impact [249]. Less frequently, the size of the BGI area or the proportion of tall greenery is examined [250]. However, due to the need to make measurements at individual points, these methods usually focus on a micro or local scale, typically involving only a few BGI objects [251]. Nevertheless, studies based on manual measurements allow for vertical T-air profile analysis, which improves the method's value over remote sensing, allowing for inferences about the causes of advection heat exchange between BGI and urban areas.

In field studies, the most commonly measured parameter is T-air, with PET being less frequent. Common UCI measurement methods include (1) comparing the average temperature inside a BGI element with the surrounding temperature [39] and (2) creating “cross-sections” through the BGI object and its surroundings from measurement points (mobile traverse/transect method) and evaluating the resulting function [38,251,252]. The second method uses mobile temperature loggers with GPS mounted on various vehicles, including bicycles [38]. This method allows multiple measurements to be performed with a single device in a short period, reducing sensor installation costs while ensuring measurement homogeneity. The calibration of results based on temporal changes in the measured parameters is necessary using the optimized reentry–transect method [251]. To maintain measurement point simultaneity, transects should be created with no more than a 2 h time gap. Often, multiple sensors are mounted on one vehicle to increase measurement frequency and accuracy. In addition to T-air, other parameters such as black globe temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, wind direction, and solar radiation are also measured [251].

Examples of research results on the features of BGI affecting its cooling potential using field measurements are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Examples of studies on the features of BGI affecting its cooling efficiency conducted using field measurements (+ and – indicate the direction of the feature's influence on cooling potential; the multiplicity of the sign indicates the relative significance of the influence).

Source	Study Region	Time of Measurements	BGI Type	Cooling Potential index	Cooling Potential Values	Method of Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	BGI Most Efficient Characteristics
Vaz Monteiro et al. [250]	London, UK	20 June 2012 to 2 October 2012 (nocturnal cooling)	Green open spaces and tree canopy	Reduction in LST; HCD	0.6–1 °C LST; HCD: 100–150 m	Temperature measurements at different distances from the BGI	Area, PARA, tree coverage, grass coverage	Area (++) Tree coverage (+) Grass coverage (+)
Spronken-Smith et al. [38]	Vancouver, BC and Sacramento, CA	July–August 1992 (Vancouver); August 1993 (Sacramento)	Green open spaces	Reduction in T-air and LST	Max 6.5 °C T-air; average (day): 2.4 °C average (night): 3.3 °C	Temperature measurements at different distances from the BGI (bicycle traverse)	Type (grass, grass with tree border, savannah, golf course, garden, multiuse, forest), tree coverage, irrigation	Tree coverage (++) Type: sparsely treed savannah park in a semi-rural settings (+) Irrigation (+)
Chang et al. [39]	Taipei, Taiwan	August–September 2003; from December 2003 to January 2004	Urban parks (61 objects)	Reduction in T-air	Mean: 0.59 °C max: 1.51 °C	T-air measurements at 2 m: inside the park and in the surroundings	Area, tree and shrub coverage, turf coverage, tree coverage	Area (<3 ha) (++) Tree coverage (+)

Table 4. Cont.

Source	Study Region	Time of Measurements	BGI Type	Cooling Potential index	Cooling Potential Values	Method of Impact Assessment	BGI Characteristics Studied	BGI Most Efficient Characteristics
Cohen et al. [78]	Tel Aviv, Israel	2007–2011	Parks, squares, street canyons	Reduction in T-air and PET	2–4.5 °C T-air 10–18 °C PET	Measurements from fixed meteorological stations	BGI type, BGI layout, tree coverage	Tree coverage (++) Deciduous trees type (+)
Hoellscher et al. [253]	Berlin, Germany	16 July 2013	Green facade	Reduction in T-air/LST	15.5 °C LST	Temperature comparison between a green wall and a standard building façade	Different plant species, various arrangements of vegetation on façades	Design of facade greenery (+) LST (+/–) T-air
Hamada and Ohta [254]	Nagoya, Japan	August 2006 to July 2007	Urban park	Reduction in T-air; HCD	0.3–1.9 °C T-air HCD: 200–300 m	Measurements from fixed meteorological stations	Forest cover ratio	Forest cover ratio (+)

6. Technologies with the Potential to Develop Tools to Optimize BGI Planning and Management

In spatial planning, BGI is one of the most effective tools for mitigating and adapting to climate change. In addition to reducing thermal stress, adaptation includes alleviating the intensity of flash floods [255], enhancing resilience to urban droughts [256], purifying the air [257], and increasing biodiversity [258]. Mitigation using BGI mainly involves carbon dioxide sequestration [21] and energy consumption reduction [244]. Optimal BGI implementation requires consideration of the relationships between all potential outcomes, not just urban thermal issues, thus ensuring that the solutions are as effective as possible overall. Given the complexity of the problem, tools based solely on numerical simulations, remote sensing, and other measurements become insufficient. In this context, more complex systems and technologies are necessary, such as digital twin (DT), defined as “a virtual representation of a physical system (and its associated environment and processes) that is updated through the exchange of information between the physical and virtual systems” [259]. A key element of DT is ensuring connectivity between the model and the real world, being closely linked with artificial intelligence (AI), Big Data (BD), the Internet of Things (IoT), and edge processing for data collection and processing, thus enabling real-time system monitoring as well as simulating changes under specific parameter modification scenarios. Although the term DT was first mentioned in the early 21st century, it has only become widespread in cities in recent years, thanks to the development of digital infrastructure and data-based technologies [260], becoming an integral part of the smart city concept [260,261].

Urban DTs are used for power grids, energy demand, renewable energy, mobility, public transportation, road infrastructure, water supply, sewage, noise pollution, flooding, and climatology [260–263], with most research focusing on their conceptualization or application within narrow industry frameworks [259,261,264–266]. However, there is limited knowledge of the creation and implementation of comprehensive DTs. In the context of BGI, despite the enormous potential and developmental capabilities of DT technology, no comprehensive system has yet been implemented for its planning and management at the urban scale, considering all ecosystem services and the level of detail needed for local planning.

DT technology for BGI planning and management should encapsulate data on key processes in urban environments across various scales. Ensuring interoperability between systems is crucial for effective information exchange and better decision making through more accurate forecasting. A promising approach is AI for managing IoT (AIoT) [267].

Current interoperability challenges include data silos from infrastructure providers [268], isolation in public sectors [269], and tight coupling of data to specific applications [263,270], along with the complexity of multiple scales and domains [271]. Additionally, data heterogeneity in scale, detail, accuracy, and spatial and temporal uniformity, combined with BGI's complex relationships with urban space, makes defining semantic rules for dynamic city representation difficult [272,273]. Creating new metadata standards and universal data exchange formats is therefore necessary for effective data fusion [260,274,275].

Infrastructure is crucial, including computing, networks, and data storage [260]. DT technologies, such as IoT [276] and increasingly detailed 3D models with augmented reality (AR) [277], require highly efficient real-time data processing [276], necessitating the development of new data processing engines [278] and edge computing architectures [279], along with higher-capacity networks. Beyond processing, data storage and archiving vast amounts of data used by DT become critical [270], and a promising direction is the development of efficient decentralized data storage architectures [279]. A key issue to address is also data acquisition [260]. Current IoT networks (e.g., Open Sense Map) may be too fragmented and heterogeneous to maintain proper temporal and spatial continuity [270]. Further challenges include synchronizing real-time measurement frequencies [261], network speed, and connectivity continuity; synchronization affects data generation, distribution, and analysis speed, which is crucial for real-time processing [260]. Additionally, despite the existence of various IoT networks, some environmental, social, or economic data are still missing, and some lack sufficient quality and reliability to ensure the accuracy and realism of DT [270,280,281].

A key challenge is ensuring an optimal modeling and simulation system for evaluating urban development scenarios, which is crucial for improving decision support systems [260]. Promising advancements in machine learning and deep learning (ML/DL) are being explored for processing data in DT [281]; however, challenges remain regarding computational limitations, integrating models at multiple scales, ensuring data quality [278,279], and managing the complexity of urban systems [282], along with a lack of sufficient validation [270], uncertainty quantification [283], and adaptation to extreme situations [272]. Maintaining informative visualizations of results is also essential, with potential in technologies such as augmented reality (AR), extended reality (XR), virtual reality (VR), and mixed reality (MR) [260].

Beyond technological challenges, the development and implementation of DT for BGI may be hindered by the need for a skilled workforce and funding to develop and maintain the infrastructure [260]. Additionally, the diverse and dispersed nature of BGI may require various sub-models to accurately simulate elements like water, vegetation, soil, heat exchange, and flood risk. Developing and operating DTs requires extensive technical expertise [261], but system developers are scarce in the urban planning and local government sectors. In interdisciplinary teams, there is often a lack of understanding among disciplines, including limited technical knowledge in local governments and dependency on external firms [284]. Furthermore, there is a lack of professional communities and training programs, leaving DT developers and practitioners without the resources or access to specialized "know-how" for specific applications [285]. Advancing DT technology thus requires both individual upskilling and interdisciplinary organizational collaboration [269] among urban planners, geographic information scientists, computer engineers, and local authorities. An effective approach could also include supporting implementation doctorates within companies or local governments with the potential to develop DT solutions. Despite these challenges, implementing DT technology in cities can significantly improve the efficiency of decision-making processes related to BGI planning and management [286]. Research focused on the development of DT for BGI should therefore be a priority in

optimizing planning and management methods, both in the conceptualization and the construction and integration of specific geoinformatics products and spatial data, to support the creation of more resilient cities.

7. Discussion

7.1. Interpretation and Findings

7.1.1. Strengths and Limitations of Different Approaches

Each approach to assessing cooling potential—remote sensing, numerical simulations, and field measurements—offers unique capabilities for analyzing BGI [100]. Numerical simulations require the most data and the most significant computational power, even for analyzing small areas [47], and are highly sensitive to input data and assumptions including initial and boundary conditions, which increases uncertainty and necessitates more robust validation. Remote sensing methods, on the other hand, can often rely on readily available products covering thousands of square kilometers [48]. However, remote sensing is limited to measuring LST within the sensor's specific angle, restricting information about urban thermal conditions, especially in areas with complex morphology [56], and focusing only on the outermost urban surface layers, which may not accurately reflect conditions experienced by residents. Field measurements require minimal data, have a high temporal resolution, and are suitable for analyzing short-term trends, but are limited by the accessibility of certain urban locations, such as private properties [287].

The research objective and scale of analysis are key in selecting the appropriate method. At the local scale, if the goal is to assess BGI characteristics relevant to urban planning (e.g., BGI area geometry, vegetation density, and urban morphology impact), remote sensing is the best choice, capturing broad spatial context and facilitating the analysis of multiple large BGI areas simultaneously, though it is effective only for evaluating existing BGI features. At the neighborhood scale, when evaluating the effectiveness of different BGI development scenarios, numerical simulations are optimal. This method supports micro-scale analysis, such as assessing solutions like green roofs and walls. Field measurements, on the other hand, excel in capturing actual atmospheric parameters necessary for calculating thermal comfort indices, providing insight into BGI's real impact on urban livability.

7.1.2. Causes of Differences Between Results Obtained Using Different Approaches

Aside from diverse urban morphology and meteorological and climatic conditions, variations in results may stem from differing definitions of BGI cooling effectiveness. For remote sensing studies, comparisons typically involve contrasting LST values within or at the edge of a BGI feature with those of the immediate surroundings, e.g., [70]. Field measurements may use the same method but focus on T-air differences, e.g., [38]. In numerical simulations, cooling effectiveness is often reflected by differences in average T-air values across the study area before and after introducing specific BGI configurations, e.g., [230]. The latter approach simulates BGI's potential impact on urban temperature reduction, offering insights into cooling effectiveness, though the results inherently carry some uncertainty. These methodological disparities, combined with the lack of correlation between LST and T-air, hinder effective result comparisons between different methodological approaches. In each case, the results reflect the impact of BGI on entirely different phenomena, which influence the amplification of HWs-related risks in distinct ways. Additionally, the representation of BGI—areas in remote sensing versus individual elements like trees or green roofs in simulations—limits the standardization of cooling values based on BGI "size". Finally, effective comparison is hindered by the different research scales, with extensive remote sensing analyses and localized simulation or field measurements results. Nonetheless, direct comparisons of maximum cooling intensity show averages of 4 °C

(LST) for remote sensing, 3 °C (T-air) for field measurements, and 2 °C (T-air) for numerical simulation, thus suggesting that numerical simulations may underestimate BGI cooling efficiency. However, it is crucial to note that these values do not represent either the same phenomena or the same efficiency indicator, and further investigation is thus required.

In the case of employing a remote sensing approach, LST resolution notably impacts the results. Studies using lower-resolution data report broader cooling extents than those based on high-resolution LST [72], indicating that “mixed pixels” might artificially expand cooling zones. This effect is particularly evident with common Landsat 8/9 data, which use TIRS images with a native 100 m resolution, downscaled to 30 m. Each 100 m pixel averages diverse urban surfaces, thus blurring BGI boundaries and potentially intensifying the gradient effect of rising LST with distance from the BGI site. Additionally, land use around the BGI can reinforce the LST gradient effect if smaller vegetation structures, like single trees or green roofs, reflect a gradient of decreasing vegetation intensity with distance from object under investigation. Building configurations that cast shadows also influence localized LST values, potentially lowering pixel readings. These challenges become less pronounced with higher-resolution imagery. Downscaled images, however, may introduce errors associated with the statistical resolution enhancement, while results may also vary due to cooling potential calculation methods, including the buffer widths and other methods used.

Another important factor affecting results is the method of BGI delimitation. Using BGI boundaries from urban databases often overlooks the actual extent of vegetation in favor of property boundaries. Such an approach is highly susceptible to errors caused by the surrounding morphology impacting cooling zone anomalies. More effective methods involve processing remote sensing imagery (e.g., image classification or vegetation index reclassification [70]), allowing for objective, uniform delineation of BGI’s physical boundaries. However, it is important to use the same imagery source for both LST calculations and BGI delimitation (e.g., Landsat 8/9—OLI bands for BGI delimitation and TIRS bands for LST calculations), minimizing errors due to georeferencing or radiometric corrections.

In numerical simulations, the largest discrepancies occur between micro- and mesoscale models [47], primarily because models at different scales apply distinct assumptions regarding physical heat exchange processes in urban spaces. Mesoscale models often simplify local phenomena, such as the cooling effect of individual trees and small green spaces, and cannot fully describe heat fluxes in urban canyons [100]. Conversely, microscale models offer more detail and can better represent these localized processes, yet they are limited in generalizing results across larger areas.

Significant differences can also be observed among models at the same scale, despite simulating identical scenarios and conditions. This variability often results from differences in how models implement and parameterize physical processes related to BGI’s cooling mechanisms in urban spaces. Models may vary in their representation of vertical heat transport and surface–atmosphere energy exchanges, which impacts outcomes.

Furthermore, a model’s ability to accurately recreate the microclimatic conditions of a specific area does not ensure its suitability for simulating BGI cooling potential. Cooling effects from evapotranspiration and shading require specific sub-models, which are not typically assessed in standard numerical simulation tests. For UCI studies, model physics evaluation should therefore be conducted with stricter criteria to enhance the reliability of simulation results [47].

In field-based studies, differences in results may arise from how microclimatic factors are recorded, such as how sensors are shielded from solar radiation. Variations can also stem from the method of data collection itself; results can differ between studies based on data from fixed monitoring stations and those using mobile recorders, as the latter may be more precise [100]. Additionally, differences may arise from time shifts in measurements

when using mobile traverse methods. It is evident that, without accounting for changes in T-air over the daily cycle, measurements taken along a transect from the studied BGI object outward may show an increasing trend, even if the object itself does not exhibit cooling properties. The use of the optimized reentry-transect method is therefore necessary [251].

7.1.3. BGI Characteristics Affecting Cooling Potential

BGI is an effective tool for mitigating both LST and T-air, improving thermal comfort and enhancing the quality of urban life and energy efficiency. In LST-based studies, the most commonly analyzed BGI characteristics impacting cooling efficiency include geometry (area, perimeter, LSI, and other perimeter/surface ratios), canopy cover, and surface water fraction [46,63,66,160,184]. Numerical simulation studies often focus on vegetation fraction and various BGI configurations (including trees and green roofs) [211,229,230,244,248]. Field measurement studies typically examine the BGI surface area and the proportion of tall vegetation [38,39,250,254]. In all cases, the most important feature is the BGI area, and most studies have shown that larger BGI objects (defined as vegetation-covered areas) cool urban spaces more intensively and over a larger scale [129,204–206]. However, the cooling capacity increase is not proportional to the increase in BGI area. Some studies suggest the need to identify the minimum area that ensures effective cooling [60], balancing economic viability and efficient space use. In addition to the BGI scale, vegetation intensity and quality are essential. In remote sensing, NDVI [66,151] or LAI can define this characteristic; in numerical simulations, LAI, LAD, or vegetation type diversity level [142,232,239]; and in field measurements, the proportion of tall vegetation [38,39,250,254]. However, adequate ventilation is also crucial, so vegetation should not be overly dense, especially within ventilation corridors [116].

Additionally, specific characteristics that can only be assessed using a single method type can be distinguished. For example, comparing the cooling efficiency of green walls and roofs to traditional BGI is feasible only through numerical simulations. Although green roofs help regulate local temperatures, they are less effective than conventional BGI [183,234] by up to 1.8 °C [229], thus limiting their cost-effectiveness to dense urban settings where creating ground-level BGI is not feasible. Another group of BGI characteristics is landscape metrics, which can only be assessed through remote sensing. In this context, the most important factor is the spatial connection of BGI [72,154].

The complexity of BGI shapes is often studied, but the results are inconsistent. The differences may stem from varying locations and climatic characteristics of the studied areas [134,160,288], as well as different interpretations of statistical analysis results. Commonly studied indicators like LSI often correlate strongly with shape area, leading to potential misinterpretations that larger LSI implies greater cooling. An additional source of uncertainty may be the varied urban morphology, which can modify the cooling potential of specific BGI shapes [35,76,106,138,140]. When evaluating the impact of shape complexity, it is therefore important to first confirm the lack of correlation with shape area and assess the effect of surrounding building morphology.

7.2. Limitations

The primary limitation of this literature review is the lack of standardization in results derived from different methods. A more detailed assessment would require linking cooling potential outcomes to a standardizing factor, such as the area of BGI objects or vegetation fraction within the study area, which would enable a comparison of the significance of differences between the groups. However, identifying a suitable standardization factor is challenging due to diverse methodologies and geographic or climatic differences. Additionally, the review employed an arbitrarily defined set of keywords for database searches.

Expanding the types of search phrases could potentially yield better results. Furthermore, no objective method was used to select equally sized sets of articles based on the specific methodology type or geographic location, potentially introducing biases.

Despite the aforementioned limitations, this review successfully achieved its objectives. The primary aim was not a precise quantitative analysis but rather the systematization of knowledge regarding methods for evaluating the cooling potential of BGI. The review included an overview of cooling mechanisms, key BGI characteristics, and available research data sources, culminating in a comprehensive interdisciplinary compendium of knowledge, offering valuable insights into the critical aspects of methods for assessing the cooling services of BGI for both researchers and practitioners.

7.3. Gaps and Future Research Directions

7.3.1. Potential Improvements of Existing Methods

Integrating remote sensing approaches with field measurements can enable better comparison of methods and more accurate assessment of UHIs, contributing to a comprehensive evaluation of BGI cooling. This integration could be achieved using geostatistical techniques, such as empirical Bayesian kriging with regression prediction, which could estimate T-air values based on correlations with LST. However, while some studies have confirmed a general relationship between LST and T-air at coarse scales [51,289–297], fewer have developed robust relationships in the morphologically complex urban spaces, due to solar intensity, surface moisture, near-surface atmospheric conditions, wind, clouds, shading, sky view factor, and sensor view angle [50–56]. These factors, along with sparse station T-air measurements, lack of sensor homogeneity, and coarse spatial resolution of model-derived urban T-air data, reduce the effectiveness of the estimation of T-air from LST in urban environments [298–301]. This indicates that, for more effective prediction using kriging techniques, a denser spatial and temporal network of measurements (e.g., mobile sensor networks) would be required. Additionally, due to the partial lack of correlation with LST, T-air regression-based kriging interpolation would necessitate the acquisition of supplementary data, such as sky view factor or the thermal capacity of urban materials. Moreover, to minimize the errors resulting from the use of either LST or T-air, it may also be effective to use hybrid methods comparing cooling capacities calculated based on LST-estimated T-air and measured T-air, taking into account the specific impacts of each indicator on various aspects of the microclimate, or studies with extended validation [129].

7.3.2. Incorporating Factors Related to Urban Morphology Around BGI

Studies on the cooling capacity of BGI features have rarely addressed the characteristics of the surrounding urban morphology, despite its potential impact on BGI's cooling ability by increasing temperature and humidity contrasts [35,76,106,184,302] and thermal stress on vegetation [45,140]. Future research should therefore place more emphasis on this aspect, with the focus on utilizing the LCZ concept. A useful tool for remote sensing could be the World Urban Database and Access Portal Tools LCZ Generator [303], which enables the semi-automatic classification of urban areas based on morphological diversity relevant to thermal dynamics.

7.3.3. Development of an Objective Method for Delimiting BGI Objects for Analysis

Regardless of the adopted definition of cooling, the delimitation of BGI shapes has the greatest impact on the obtained results. Therefore, it is essential to use objective methods for delimiting BGI objects. One such method can be Geographic Object-Based Image Analysis (GEOBIA) [304,305], preferably performed using the same image employed to calculate the LST data.

7.3.4. Integration of New Spatial Data

An important direction should be the integration of new, less explored, spatial data, such as ECOSTRESS LST. Such analyses could shed new light on the changes in the cooling potential of BGI over a 24 h cycle, including at night, which would be important, for example, in assessing the impact of BI on nocturnal SUHI. It is also necessary to aim for higher-resolution LST data [160] and greater engagement of IoT, which could assist in both the better validation of CFD studies and accuracy of T-air estimations from LST using geostatistical techniques. Additionally, UAV measurements [306] offer promising potential for validating simulations and providing precise thermal data, especially for surfaces inaccessible using standard remote sensing, thus achieving more accurate assessments of BGI characteristics.

7.3.5. Research on a Large Scale or the Integration of Results into a Universal Indicator

Different climates and geographic locations can significantly impact the results of BGI's cooling potential. An objective assessment of BGI characteristics requires analyzing cases from various contexts. To achieve this, studies should be expanded based on automated analytical procedures that facilitate the simultaneous analysis of multiple cities using a unified method (e.g., [141]), or through literature reviews that incorporate standardization of results, e.g., [47]. Developing methods for standardizing outcomes from various approaches is thus crucial.

7.3.6. Correct Interpretation of Results Obtained Using LST

The results of remote sensing analyses represent not perceived temperature but rather LST, influenced by emissivity and other physical parameters of different surface configurations. BGI affects LST primarily through shading and evapotranspiration, which is well documented. However, the cooling mechanisms of LST in areas distant from BGI require further research and validation to address resolution and urban morphology issues.

7.3.7. Development of Comprehensive Urban Ventilation Models

Wind conditions modify BGI cooling capacity and thermal comfort. Effective BGI management requires detailed city-wide ventilation simulations that consider urban morphology and BGI features. However, current CFD models are scale-limited, partly due to computational constraints. Advancing CFD and related technologies with AI support (e.g., graph neural networks [307]) is therefore essential.

7.3.8. Use of the Digital Twin Technology

There is a need to unify approaches for assessing the cooling potential of BGIs and standardize data for interoperable solutions. Future BGI research should move away from traditional methodologies towards revolutionary concepts like DT. It is essential to combine AI, IoT, and BD technologies with the practical needs of implementing DT in cities for optimizing BGI planning and management. The main challenges include the following: (1) interoperability and semantics; (2) computational infrastructure, networks, and data storage; (3) data acquisition, synchronization, and updating; (4) data quality and harmonization; (5) modeling and simulation of real phenomena, as well as integration with decision-making systems; (6) visualization informativeness; (7) human and financial resources; and (8) legislative, organizational, and social issues [260]. These topics require the most attention in future research to enable the creation and implementation of holistic tools for optimizing BGI planning and management to enhance cities' resilience to climate change.

8. Conclusions

This study aimed to systematize knowledge through a literature review of studies on the use of geoinformatics tools and spatial data to assess BGI cooling potential for sustainable urban planning optimization. The main conclusions include the following:

- The key BGI features enhancing cooling efficiency, regardless of the method used, include the shape area, vegetation density, foliage density, multi-level structure, and spatial connectivity. It remains unclear whether the shape complexity positively influences the cooling ability of BGI in every morphological context; however, it has a positive effect on BGI cooling in high-density urban areas.
- Numerical simulations show that green roofs and walls are less effective than traditional BGI types by up to 1.8 °C.
- The surrounding urban morphology also affects cooling through further modifying the park-breeze effect and thermal stress on vegetation. BGI adjacent to more intensive urban development can cool the surrounding area by 393 m further and by 10 °C more effectively.
- Methods such as remote sensing, numerical simulations, and field measurements vary in their analytical capabilities, which differentiates their effectiveness to fulfill specific research needs. The remote sensing approach compares LST inside and around BGI, numerical simulations analyze mean temperature changes before and after BGI implementation, and field measurements focus on T-air differences within specific locations.
- Remote sensing is particularly effective for analyzing large numbers of extensive BGI objects, such as parks, lakes, river valleys, and urban forests, due to its data scale and utility in geographic information systems, making it ideal for city-scale urban planning. Numerical simulations are more effective for evaluating the cooling potential of different configurations of smaller-scale features like individual trees, lawns, green roofs, and green walls, making them ideal for verifying the effectiveness of various BGI development scenarios at the neighborhood scale for local and detailed urban planning. Field measurements, typically focused on fewer objects such as urban parks at a local scale or green roofs and walls on a micro scale, are particularly effective in assessing individual BGI elements and their impacts on perceived microclimate conditions, thereby contributing to local and detailed urban planning.
- Methodological differences between the analyzed approaches prevent direct comparisons of the results. Nonetheless, maximum cooling intensity averages show 4 °C (LST) from remote sensing, 3 °C (T-air) from field measurements, and 2 °C (T-air) from numerical simulations. Remote sensing analyses tend to overestimate cooling effects, especially with low-resolution data. Numerical simulations may tend to underestimate the cooling efficiency of BGI, but further investigation is necessary to confirm this trend.
- Apart from the typological diversity of the studied BGI types and the methodological diversity of approaches, results may also vary due to geographical and climatic differences, as well as in reference to cooling efficiency definitions, data resolution, BGI delimitation methods, and the types of simulation models used.
- Key research gaps include: (1) further studies on the impact of BGI shape complexity on cooling efficiency, particularly regarding its effect on plant thermal stress, (2) the search for effective methods to integrate approaches for results' comparisons, with a focus on standardizing BGI intervention intensity across methods, (3) deepening the understanding of the urban morphology's impact on the modification of BGI cooling effects, especially to confirm positive or negative influences of building density on plant thermal stress and the park-breeze effect, (4) T-air estimation based on

LST, using geostatistics or machine learning, (5) and integrating new spatial data, including nighttime and UAV LST, and meteorological data from IoT, to achieve more precise urban thermal assessments. A promising research direction is the development of digital twin technology for BGI planning and management optimization, which could maximize BGI-related benefits through advanced simulations and monitoring processes. However, challenges remain in implementing this technology, including data and model semantics, data quality, real-time simulations, and the need for an interdisciplinary, skilled workforce.

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